

THE BOT FRAMEWORK

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INTRODUCTION

HUMAN-ROBOT INTERACTION

With the advancements in today's technology, we are enabling an important concept, which Harry Shum (*#MSBuild 2017, p. 2*) just simply calls the *Conversational AI*¹. We might be the eyewitnesses of the next user interface paradigm shift. From command line we changed to graphical user interface and now is the time for the *brave new world* where computers understand humans.

The *Bot Framework* is a platform (*BFD, 2017a*) from Microsoft for building powerful and intelligent bots. The Framework consists of the following three main components: Bot Builder SDK with support for .NET and Node.js, the Bot Connector service, and the Developer Portal.

Bots are just applications with a new interface: the user interaction is performed via conversations so that we can also refer to them as *chatbots*.

PERSONAL MOTIVATION

I find chatbots fascinating. The back-end services of the whole ecosystem that produce a strong enthusiasm and interest from my side. I have always had a passion for Distributed System Architecture, APIs and Business Process Automation.

It was settled that I would choose Microsoft's framework in preference to any other available systems due to its support of their cloud artificial intelligence APIs, the Cognitive Services (*CSD, 2017a*). It is an impressive wide-range set of AI algorithms from computer vision and speech, through emotion recognition and sentiment analysis to natural language processing.

Working with API.AI² was my very first experience of building a chatbot last year. It is a natural language processing platform, which has been acquired by Google (*'List of mergers', n.d.*) in

¹ Conversational AI = Cognitive Services + Bot Framework

² <https://api.ai/>

September 2016. If we can rely on the 'toothbrush test'³ (Gelles, 2014) of Google CEO Larry Page: chatbots are the kind of trend in technology worth to follow.

From a business point of view, bots can do the repetitive processes, while humans take care of the rest. Chatbots are not only gaining popularity globally, according to a survey by LivePerson (as cited in Beaver, para. 11, 2017), but they allow businesses to engage with more consumers.

PROBLEM DEFINITION

With the following statement of the problem formulation (Bwisa, 2017) I attempt to conceptualise the research problem as a *Descriptive Research Problem*. The purpose is to describe the significance and the existence of the chatbots and their underlying ecosystem.

THE RESEARCH STATEMENT

To effectively engage and to take an active part in their learning, EASJ students need to access and find relevant and up-to-date information about their exams, activity plans, electives, and general administration. There is, however, a digital learning platform called Fronter, but it is, unfortunately, unfavourable on mobile devices. Without alternatives to getting the required information, the absenteeism⁴ and the undermotivation are likely to continue amongst the students. Thus, there is a need to examine other, more user-friendly ways which are the aim of this research.

QUESTIONS

The problem definition and the research statement calls the following questions into two separate groups. The *WHAT* questions refer to the analytical investigation of the subject, and the *HOW* questions will assist in developing a proof-of-concept for the research statement.

- What are the Bot Framework and its key concepts?
- What are the biggest promises of Microsoft for the developers using their platform?
- How to design and develop a chatbot?

³ „When deciding whether Google should spend millions or even billions of dollars in acquiring a new company, its chief executive, Larry Page, asks whether the acquisition passes the toothbrush test: Is it something you will use once or twice a day, and does it make your life better?“ (Gelles, 2014)

⁴ the habit of not being at school or work when you should be, usually without a good reason

- How to add artificial intelligence to bots with the Cognitive Services APIs?

Thus, the methodology of the synopsis is to split into two separate categories.

METHODOLOGY

The selected methodologies are:

- Analysis of the related technical documentation and online tutorials (*docs.microsoft.com*, *blogs.msdn.microsoft.com*, *channel9.msdn.com*) and the official open source repositories on *github.com/Microsoft*
- Practical hands-on lab experience by developing a bot with the Bot Builder SDK

OVERALL PLANNING

The approach to managing the progress of this project is a combination of some of the best practices from the agile and the lean development processes.

1. *Requirements analysis*: reading of the synopsis curriculum, asking questions from the supervisor, clarifying all the formal requirements upfront
2. *Analysis*: skimming through all the available resources of the technical documentation and making notes, also summarising the main arguments into OneNote
3. *Design & Implementation*: developing a mock chatbot which can respond to general queries regarding student activities, focusing on features adding value (good enough for running a demo) and eliminating everything else
4. *Production*: writing the project report, preparation for the presentation, making a demo

The following picture (see *Figure 1.*) illustrates my time estimation for the synopsis as a single line chart. Partly it complies with the agile approach; the progress is incremental and iterative due to the weekly feedback provided by the supervisor.

For the sake of simplicity, every phase described in the previous paragraph above, shown as *Research* (See *Figure 1.*), and any turning points or milestones in the process are highlighted.

Figure 1

THE BOT FRAMEWORK AND ITS ECOSYSTEM

At the beginning of my research, I start by defining what the Bot Framework and the chatbots are. Before choosing a suitable design pattern to build upon my project, I will discuss the main principles of the bot design. After the design recommendations, I propose guidelines to avoid common pitfalls and bad practices. Then I begin to develop a bot as a proof-of-concept that complies with basic requirements. Finally, I close the synopsis with the conclusion and my reflections. At last, I describe what I am going to present at the exam which will ideally assist me to answer my last research question.

EXPLORATION OF THE BOTS

Bots and chatbots have indeed become buzzwords these days. There is a couple of common misconception about what bots are (*Harrison, Volum and Hurlburt, 2017*):

- ⊗ *Artificial Intelligence*: bots can be just simple automation utilities, as resetting a password or booking a table at a restaurant.
- ⊗ *Text interfaces only*: it is possible to have a conversation with a chatbot without using natural language, the interaction can involve buttons, images, graphs or even speech.
- ⊗ *Natural Language Processing*: bots can use as simple commands as regular expressions.

Despite the fact that they are personified most of the time, bots are just applications with a new interface. A chatbot is an experience delivered within an existing messaging platform.

WHAT IS THE BOT FRAMEWORK?

The Bot Framework is an open source and free platform from Microsoft⁵ that provides tools for building chatbots (*BFD, 2017h*).

- *Bot Builder SDKs*: can be installed as a NuGet package⁶ which includes rich features for constructing bots (libraries, recognizers, event-handlers and built-in dialogues). The Channel Emulator, a desktop application for testing and debugging a bot hosted either remotely or locally.
- *Bot Connector*: a service that is relaying messages between the bot and the host applications, called channels, by providing industry standard *REST* and *JSON over HTTPS*
- *Developer Portal*: an online dashboard interface⁷ for registering the bot, configuring channels and running diagnostic tools

WHY CHOOSE THE BOT FRAMEWORK?

A year after the launch, the framework is now used by more than 130.000 developers (*Johnson, 2017*). What are the biggest promises of Microsoft?

Essentially a single bot is built and then rolled out to multiple channels or canvasses without any further customization. Currently, the platform supports up to fifteen channels (such as Facebook Messenger, Slack, SMS, email, Web Chat) including Microsoft's own premiers (like Skype, Cortana, Microsoft Teams, Bing, GroupMe). All settings are pre-configured on the Developer Portal with an easy-to-follow walkthrough about how to integrate the bot with the hosting applications. With tools like Adaptive Cards,⁸ the UI content can be rendered natively, to get the look and feel of each channel.

⁵ <https://github.com/Microsoft/BotBuilder>

⁶ <https://www.nuget.org/packages/Microsoft.Bot.Builder/>

⁷ <https://dev.botframework.com/>

⁸ <http://adaptivecards.io/>

Furthermore, via the Direct Line REST API tool of the Bot Connector, developers can connect directly from their client application, web chat controls or mobile apps. This API makes it possible to empower existing applications and services with a conversational user interface.

Microsoft has its own massive range (*currently offers 29 solutions*) of cloud-based *Cognitive Services*⁹ APIs with the power of machine learning and AI algorithms. A developer can enhance conversational intelligence using LUIS¹⁰ (*Language Understanding Intelligent Service*) that integrates seamlessly with the Bot Framework and enables the bot to understand human language and react accordingly.

PRINCIPLES OF BOT DESIGN

From a developer perspective, one needs to create a bot that solves a set of business problems. I will discuss a variety of concepts, and best practices (*BFD, 2017b*) suggested by Microsoft in the following paragraphs. The guidelines assume our bot will provide a preferable user experience over the alternatives like websites, apps or even phone calls.

What are the features that *will not* guarantee a bot's success?

- *How smart the bot is*: most of the cases making the bot smarter will not necessarily make the users happy.
- *Natural language support*: being a great conversationalist without addressing the problems that the users need to solve will contribute very little to engaging users.

What qualities *will influence* a bot's success?

- The bot needs to solve the user's problem with the *minimum number of steps* possible, and
- it needs to solve it *faster, better* or *easier* than the alternatives (focus on user experience).
- The bot needs to run on the channels and platforms that the users interact with.
- The best UX does not require the users to type or talk too much, nor to repeat themselves, neither explain obvious things that the bot should know by itself already.

⁹ <https://azure.microsoft.com/en-us/services/cognitive-services/>

¹⁰ <https://www.luis.ai/>

THE FIRST INTERACTION

Designing an app/website and a bot has much in common. The first ‘screen’ needs to provide navigation cues with an intuitive user interface (BFD, 2017c). The user’s first interaction with the

Figure 2

bot has to provide information like where the menu is and how it works, where to go for help rather than just saying “Hi” (see Figure 2). It is paramount to let the users know what the bot can do by narrowing the scope of the input.

MODELLING THE CONVERSATION

There are different type of tools available for various business scenarios (Mann, 2017). The challenge that the bot is supposed to solve determines the *mechanism* of the conversations.

1. *QnA Maker*: the simplest bot for answering Frequently Asked Questions (FAQs), can be implemented literally in minutes time by using *Microsoft QnA Maker REST API*¹¹. There’s no real conversation, just question-answer pairs.
2. *FormFlow*: the conversation is managed and guided by automatically generated dialogues, the main purpose is data-capturing in scenarios like ASP.NET Web Forms

¹¹ <https://qnamaker.ai/>

3. *Dialogs*: to manage multi-layered conversations that provide flexibility and support high interactivity to comply with the vision for the Conversation as a Platform (*'Microsoft outlines', 2016*) emphasised by Microsoft CEO Satya Nadella.

DIALOGS IN THE BOT BUILDER SDK FOR .NET

This research will focus solely on the latter. Dialogs¹² provide great flexibility for ever changing business scenarios and requirements, and I intend to build on them when modelling a proof-of-concept for my research statement.

Bots have User Interface, as well as apps or websites, but instead of screens, it is made up of *Dialogs* (BFD, 2017d). Dialogs logically separate functionality and control the conversational flow.

A Dialog can contain a combination of text (sometimes including natural language) or rich user controls (buttons, videos, images, and carousels) and even speech. Dialogs can also include actions to perform tasks which can either process the user's input or invoke further Dialogs.

The Bot Builder SDK for .NET delivers *them* as components, which are C# classes implementing the *IDialog* interface. The state of the conversation is automatically stored and handled by the *Bot Framework State* service (BFD 2017f). The Bot Framework Service enables the bot to store and retrieve data (*state of the conversation*) that is associated with the user, the Dialog stack and the state of each Dialog in the stack. The main purposes are to determine where the conversation is left off, to store user identity and input, which allows the user to return anytime without starting over the conversation.

- > *Dialogs are reusable and serializable classes and perform a single operation.*
- > *Dialogs are callable from other Dialogs*
- > *The main Dialog is the RootDialog, and a bot can have only ever one. The RootDialog is called when no other Dialog is currently on the stack, or no other Dialog is triggered.*

¹² Note: 'Dialog' (*American spelling*) is referring to the C# class and 'dialogue' (*British spelling*) is referring to the process of discussion

CONVERSATION-FLOW AND NAVIGATION

*Think of a bot as an ASP.NET Web API listening for POST messages (sent from the Bot Connector) sitting on the following endpoint:
"https://your_bots_hostname/api/messages"*

The *RootDialog* is first invoked when the user sends the first message to the bot (See *Code Snippet 1 in Appendices*).

After a Dialog is invoked, it takes control of the conversation, which means that every new message from the user is a subject to processing by the current Dialog. The “management” of user inputs goes until it closes or redirects to another Dialog.

DIALOG LIFECYCLE AND STACKING

Changing between messages and Dialogs is called *state-transition* (See *Code Snippet 2 in Appendices*). When one Dialog invokes another, the Bot Builder adds the new Dialog to the top of the Dialog stack (*BFD, 2017g*). The concept of the construction and deconstruction of the Dialog stack is called *layering* (See *Figure 3*).

To invoke another Dialog, or close it and remove it from the stack, every Dialog must end with a redirection method call to accomplish conversation flow and state-transition.

- > [Context.Wait\(\)](#): it instructs the bot to wait for the user to provide a message. Once the response is received, it continues the conversation within the same Dialog (See *Code Snippet 2 & 4 in Appendices*)
- > [Context.Call\(\)](#) & [Context.Forward\(\)](#): invokes another Dialog, adding it to the top of the stack, with or without passing a message to the child Dialog (See *Code Snippet 2 in Appendices*).
- > [Context.Done\(\)](#): it completes the current Dialog, closing and removing it from the stack, sending the user back to the previous Dialog in the stack (See *Code Snippet 3 in Appendices*).

Conversation

Dialog stack

Figure 3

POORLY DESIGNED CONVERSATIONAL INTERFACES

Humans do not communicate in stacks like bots do. They tend to give different input or ask a question that is not related to the current Dialog. Since users might interact with bots in a non-linear fashion, the design should consider some critical features and ensure that the *user*:

- > does not get lost in a conversation
- > can navigate back or cancel an operation during a conversation, and will find a way to reset the conversation to the “main menu.”

Regardless of the bot’s functionality, there are some common problems and difficulties, so-called “pitfalls” (BFD, 2017e) which are the result of the poor conversational interface design.

1. The ‘stubborn bot’: insist upon maintaining the current Dialog, even though the user attempts to drive the dialogue in a different direction (See Figure 4.)

Figure 4

Recommendations from Microsoft (*Ibid.*) suggest the following practices to avoid developing a ‘stubborn bot’:

- > *Design your bot to ignore certain input and avoid repeating the same question in an endless loop*
 - > *The easiest way to prevent your bot to stuck in the loop is to maximise the attempts for each question*
2. The 'mysterious bot': fails to acknowledge the user's input immediately. The user might suggest that there's a system outage. However, it could be that the bot is still processing the user's input and hasn't finished yet compiling its response (See *Figure 5*.)

Figure 5

- > *Design the bot to acknowledge user input immediately, or*
- > *To postpone acknowledgement until it finishes compiling the response with sending a typing activity (pretending that the bot is typing a response).*

3. The 'clueless bot': responds with a non-sensible manner when the user attempts to access certain functionality (See Figure 6.)

Figure 6

- > Implement 'global message handlers' (globally registered Dialogs) to examine user input for specific keywords ('help,' 'cancel,' 'start over,' 'main menu')
- > Each and every Dialog should check user input against a list of keywords, and ignore if necessary

HANDS-ON LAB

For the exam and the presentation I am building a chatbot and using Dialogs for modelling the conversation flow, and language understanding integration (*LUIS API from the Cognitive Services*). The project will be available on GitHub: <https://github.com/ystvan/chatbot101>

CONCLUSION

The aim of my project was to discover the Bot Framework on a high-level so that my findings would give me the opportunity to explore how chatbots work. The problem definition was defined accordingly.

However, the scope of the synopsis was only to reveal sufficient information for developing a proof-of-concept "*Fronter-chatbot*". In the research statement, I deliberately wrote that there is a need to examine other, more user-friendly ways of acquiring the relevant information. Why would you choose a chatbot over a Fronter webpage? Microsoft laid it out very clearly: bots are very adaptive, the users can talk to them, type to them or can tap on things, like Adaptive Cards. The Framework is allowing businesses to take their User Interface, and to bring it whatever channels or canvasses their users are.

What are the Bot Framework and its key concepts?

The Framework is a platform from Microsoft for building bots. A chatbot can be built using C# or Node.js. The *Conversation as a Platform* vision enables the businesses to engage more users.

What are the biggest promises of Microsoft for the developers using their platform?

Build one bot, connect it to everywhere. The bot is very adaptive; the UI content can be rendered natively to the hosting applications and channels.

How to design and develop a chatbot?

A lot hinges upon the business problem which the bot is trying to solve. It is a relatively new era, the design patterns and principles are still being figured out. However, traditional application and bot development have a lot in common: separating concerns and business logic the same way:

Dialogs are for bots, like screens are for apps. For user adoption, a great User Experience is a paramount design aspect.

How to add artificial intelligence to bots with the Cognitive Services APIs?

I've been building a chatbot for the exam and will present the language understanding integration.

There are *bot-patterns*, several domains where bots can be useful. Most of the use-cases can be implemented with the Bot Framework, but it is out of the scope of my research. It is worth mentioning some of them: *Task Automation* (password resetter), *Knowledge Base* (FAQ bots and QnA maker) *Handoff-to-human* (Services Desk case escalation) *Bots in apps and websites* (e-commerce backchanneling).

REFLECTIONS

Microsoft has come a long way since the release in 2016, despite the fact that the Framework, as well as most of the services, are still in preview, and the General Availability is only expected around November (*Mullins, Kannan and Nielsen, 2017*).

After finishing my research, I still have the same level of commitment to the Framework, however as a closure thought I would like to emphasise some limitations of developing a bot with the platform:

- ⊗ The main drawback is that you must register your bot on the Developer Portal before others can use it and there is no option for private or on-premises usage
- ⊗ Developers must abide by Microsoft's Terms of Use, Privacy Statement and Code of Conduct to participate

My original idea was to build a bot using the Bot Builder SDK for Node.js so at the same time I would get some more hands-on experience with JavaScript and a new framework too. I must admit, the Bot Framework itself has grown so extensive, that I had to focus on particular parts of it to fit into the constraints of the synopsis. This is the reason why Node.js was disregarded.

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APPENDICES

CITATION STYLE AND USAGE OF THE IN-TEXT REFERENCES

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LIST OF FIGURES

Figures 2-6: Own vector creations, were made using Microsoft Visio Pro 2013, the avatar vector graphics are purchased from <https://www.colourbox.dk> via a student subscription which has been provided by EASJs communications department

CODE SNIPPETS

> Code Snippet 1 in MessagesController.cs

```
namespace Bot_Application101
{
    [BotAuthentication]
    public class MessagesController : ApiController
    {
        /// <summary>
        /// POST: api/Messages
        /// Receive a message from a user and reply to it
        /// </summary>
        public async Task<HttpResponseMessage> Post([FromBody]Activity activity)
        {
            if (activity.Type == ActivityTypes.Message)
            {
                //Redirect to the Root Dialog
                await Conversation.SendAsync(activity, ()=> new RootDialog());
            }

            var response = Request.CreateResponse(HttpStatusCode.OK);
            return response;
        }
    }
}
```

> Code Snippet 2 in RootDialog.cs

```
[Serializable]
public class RootDialog : IDialog<Command>
{
    public async Task StartAsync(IDialogContext context)
    {
        // State transition: the RootDialog initiates and waits for the next message from the user
        // When message arrives, call MessageReceivedStartAsync
        context.Wait(MessageReceivedStartAsync);
    }
    public async Task MessageReceivedStartAsync(IDialogContext context, IAwaitable<IMessageActivity> argument)
    {
        // send message to user
        var message = Cards.CreateRootDialogHeroCard(context.MakeMessage(), $"Hi! How can I help you?",
            new string[] {"Synopsis info", "Internship info"});

        await context.PostAsync(message);
        // State transition: wait for the user to respond
        context.Wait(MessageReceivedOperationChoice);
    }
    public async Task MessageReceivedOperationChoice(IDialogContext context, IAwaitable<IMessageActivity> argument)
    {
        // We have a message from the user!
        var message = await argument;

        if (message.Text.Equals("Synopsis info", StringComparison.InvariantCultureIgnoreCase))
        {
            // User chose 'Synopsis' info, so invoke the 'Check Synopsis Dialog' and wait for it to finish
            // Then call ResumeAfterChildDialog (callback function)
            context.Call<object>(new CheckSynopsisDialog(), ResumeAfterChildDialog);
        }
        else if (message.Text.Equals("Internship info", StringComparison.InvariantCultureIgnoreCase))
        {
            context.Call<object>(new CheckInternshipDialog(), ResumeAfterChildDialog);
        }
        else
        {
            // User sent something else, for simplicity, ignore this input and wait for the next message
            context.Wait(MessageReceivedStartAsync);
        }
        await context.PostAsync(message);
    }
}
// ... other sections omitted for brevity
```

> Code Snippet 3 in CheckSynopsisDialog.cs

```
// ... other sections omitted for brevity
private async Task ResumeAfterSynopsisDialog(IDialogContext context, IAwaitable<object> result)
{
    // State transition - complete this Dialog and remove it from the stack
    context.Done<object>(new object());
}
}
```

> Code Snippet 4 in RootDialog.cs

```
// ... other sections omitted for brevity

private async Task ResumeAfterChildDialog(IDialogContext context, IAwaitable<object> result)
{
    var message = Cards.CreateRootDialogHeroCard(context.MakeMessage(), $"Hi! How can I help you?",
        new string[] { "Synopsis info", "Internship info" });

    await context.PostAsync(message);

    // State transition - wait for 'operation choice' message from user (loop back)
    context.Wait(MessageReceivedOperationChoice);
}
}
```

ARCHITECTURE OF THE BOT FRAMEWORK

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